

GASIFICATION OF OLIVE MILL SOLID WASTE USING A LAB-SCALE FLUIDIZED BED REACTOR

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ABSTRACT: This study focuses on lab-scale fluidized bed reactor gasification of olive mill waste and the effect of different parameters on the product gas and gasification procedure stability. Olive mill residue is a bioresource, actively produced in the Mediterranean area. This study aims to define the optimal conditions for olive mill residues gasification in the most efficient way. Another important outcome should be dealing with operational problems, such as agglomeration and tar reduction. For the purpose of this study, olive residues were gasified, testing the effect of different temperatures (700-885°C), equivalence ratios (ER ~ 0.25 – 0.35), addition of steam (air/steam gasification), and type of bed material (silica sand, olivine) on the quality of the product gas.

Keywords: biomass, gasification, bubbling fluidized bed reactor, olive mill residue, solid waste.

1 INTRODUCTION

Based on the European Regulations, regarding the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources, EU implements mandatory national targets of at least a 20% share of energy from renewable sources in the Community's gross final consumption of energy by 2020. Although, the targets are precisely stated with respect to different countries, where Cyprus will have to have 13% of renewable energy in the total energy consumption.[1]

Biomass, as carbon-neutral energy source, can significantly contribute to the global struggle for achieving the rise of RE in the total energy mix. Gasification is the thermochemical transformation of solid or liquid biomass into a mixture of carbon monoxide, hydrogen, carbon dioxide, methane, tar, water vapor, hydrogen sulphide and other trace species whose fractions are determined by operational variables such as raw material characteristics, gasifying media (steam, air, O₂, CO₂), temperature and pressure inside the gasifier, and catalysts (if used).[2][3] The biomass gasification represents an efficient process for the production of power and heat and the production of hydrogen and second - generation biofuels.[4]

Biomass gasification occurs through a sequence of complex thermochemical reactions and hence, it is unrealistic to split the gasifier into different zones carrying out many gasification reactions simultaneously.[5] Every fuel requires some amount of oxygen to carry out the process of combustion. The stoichiometric air to fuel ratio required for the complete combustion of biomass fuel varies from 6:1 to 6.5:1 with CO₂ and H₂O as the end products. However, the gasification process requires less amount of oxygen resulting to incomplete biomass combustion at sub-stoichiometric air to fuel ratio varying from 1.5:1 to 1.8:1.[6]

To achieve a high carbon conversion of the biomass and low tar content in the resultant product gas, a high operating temperature (above 800° C) in the gasifier is preferred. More than 40% reduction in tar yield was reported when the temperature was raised from 700°C to 900°C. With increase in temperature, the amount of total oxygen-containing components drastically goes down, the amount of substituted 1-ring and 2-ring aromatics also decrease, but formation of 3- and 4-ring aromatics increases rapidly. Almost 40% increase in naphthalene content was reported at 900°C.[7] By changing the bed temperature of the bubbling fluidized bed from 700°C to

850°C, there has been an observation of an increase in H₂ content from 5 to 10 vol%, CO content from 12 to 18 vol%, slight decrease in CO₂ content from 16 to 13 vol% and almost no change in the amount of CH₄ and C₂H₂. [8]

Different gasifying agents such as air, steam, steam-oxygen and carbon dioxide have been reported in the literature. Selectivity of the gasification reactions varies with different gasifying media, thus affecting the product gas composition as well as the heating value. The heat content of the product gas is a function of the gasifier environment.

Equivalence ratio is another important factor, affecting biomass gasification. The equivalence ratio (ER) represents the actual air-to-biomass ratio with respect to the stoichiometric requirement for complete conversion and plays a key role in biomass gasification. [9] Higher ER results in lower H₂ and CO yields, with an increase in CO₂, which in turn decreases the heat content of the syngas. By contrast, a higher ER improves tar cracking due to higher O₂ availability for volatile species to react with. [10]

There are different types of gasifiers, mainly based on how the biomass is supported in the reactor vessel, the direction of flow of both the biomass and the oxidant, and the way the heat is supplied to the reactor. The design of a biomass gasifier depends on the fuel availability, its shape and size, the moisture content, the ash content and the end user applications. For the purpose of this research, a bubbling fluidized bed gasifier was used.

Foundation of this type of gasifier is based on the principle of fluidization in which both the fuel and inert bed material behaves like a fluid. Such behavior is observed when the fluidization medium like air, steam, oxygen, and their mixture is allowed to force through the solid inventory of the reactor. These gasifiers employ back mixing which leads to the efficient mixing of the feedstock particles with the particles already undergoing gasification. Silica has been considered as the most commonly used inert bed material for these type of gasifiers, however, other bulk solids such as, sand, olivine, glass beads, dolomite etc.

The basic concept of fluidized bed has been adopted to enhance the heat transfer between the fuel particles for better gasification process and therefore, a fluidized bed can operate under nearly isothermal conditions. Operating temperature of a fluidized bed reactor depends on the melting point of bed material and generally varies from

800 to 900 °C, which is relatively low and hence, gasification reactions do not reach at chemical equilibrium at such low temperature conditions unless any catalyst is used. Short gas residence time is also another cause of not achieving a chemical equilibrium. Due to these factors, hydrocarbon contents in producer gas in case of the fluidized bed reactor fall in the range of the fixed bed gasifier. However, the carbon conversion efficiency of these gasifiers is comparatively high and reported to be up to 95%. [11][12]

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 WOB lab-scale fluidized bed gasifier

For the purpose of this study, olive residues from olive oil mills in Cyprus were gasified in the WOB lab-scale fluidized bed reactor. The operating conditions, such as ER, Temperature, gasifying agent (air/nitrogen, steam) and bed materials were changing throughout the experiments in order to see their effect on the product gas quality and composition.

The WOB fluidized bed reactor at ECN, Netherlands was used for the purpose of the experiments. The WOB reactor is a multi-purpose reactor for bubbling fluidized bed (BFB) gasification, combustion and pyrolysis of approximately 0.5 kg/h fuel. The inner diameter of the reactor is 74 mm (at the position of the bed) and widens to 108 mm (at the position of the freeboard). The temperature of the electrically heated reactor wall can be controlled independently of the fuel used and enables the simulation of adiabatic conditions.[13]

The reactor can be electrically heated to as high as 1100°C and can be fluidized with air, steam, oxygen, nitrogen or other gases. Further, pressure differences over the bed region as well as different local temperatures within the reactor are monitored. A combination of air and nitrogen has been used as the fluidization medium in all experiments performed. Though, steam was also introduced as a fluidization medium on some occasions.[13] Figure 1 depicts a schematic layout of the WOB reactor is provided. [14]

Figure 1: WOB lab-scale fluidized bed reactor schematic layout

The main objective of this study was to determine the desirable conditions of gasification of the selected fuel (olive residue), based on documented properties of this feedstock. [15] [16] [17].

The first test series of gasification were carried out in the temperature ranges of 650 – 750 °C, slowly increasing as the tests were proceeding. Air/nitrogen mixture was set to be a gasifying agent with the feed of air = 10.5NL/min decreasing to 7.5NL/min and N₂ of 4.5NL/min (+1NL/min from the feeding screw) increasing to 7.5NL/min (+1NL/min from the feeding screw) as the experiment proceeded. As a result, those conditions gave ER decrease from 0.35 to 0.25, respectively. The bed material used with the above conditions was silica sand.

The effect of water gasification was also tested by adding 0.1kg/h and then 0.2kg/h of steam, resulting in 14.71 wt% steam and 25.64 wt% steam respectively.

The second test series were carried out with olivine as the bed material. The temperature range was 700 - 850°C. As before, air/N₂ mixture served as a gasifying agent with the air flow of 9.5NL/min decreasing to 7.5NL/min and N₂ flow of 5.5NL/min (+1NL/min from the feeding screw) increasing to 7.5NL/min (+1NL/min from the feeding screw) as the experiment proceeded. ER was slowly decreasing over time from 0.317 to 0.25.

Water gasification was also implemented with the same parameters, as described in the first test series.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to the high variation of gasification conditions, broad data was collected, which allowed indicative results to be delivered. For all the tests, fuel feeding rate was approximately 0.5kg/h. Table I and II represent the findings of Cold Gas Efficiency and Gas Yield for different operational conditions, respectively.

Table I: Cold Gas Efficiency results

Conditions	Cold Gas Efficiency (%)			
ER	0.35	0.317	0.283	0.25
Silica sand, T = 660 - 740°C	29.00	25.68	22.65	27.46
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	-	-	29.80
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	33.02	32.45	30.78
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	35.17
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	40.10
Olivine, T = 750°C	-	27.55	31.06	35.48
Olivine, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	43.57
Olivine, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	49.45
Olivine, T = 840°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	61.15

Table II: Gas Yield results

Conditions	Gas Yield (NL/kg)				
	ER	0.35	0.317	0.283	0.25
Silica sand, T = 660 - 740°C	1456.51	1330.11	1225.99	1206.34	
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	-	-	1218.60	
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	1358.52	1292.52	1206.22	
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	1295.06	
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	1401.47	
Olivine, T = 750°C	-	1395.71	1365.4	1271.48	
Olivine, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	1453.07	
Olivine, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	1577.29	
Olivine, T = 840°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	1730.19	

The tables above indicate the effect of ER, Temperature, bed material and gasifying agent (air/N₂, steam) on two crucial parameters of gasification procedure. For silica sand, decrease of ER with the rest conditions unchanged provides a steady decrease in both CGE and GY. This can be explained by higher tar content in the product gas due to less oxidation. On the other hand, lower ER results in higher contents of H₂ and CO, which, in return, increases the heating value of the product gas. T increase, on the other hand, results in higher values of both CGE and GY. The drawback of higher temperatures in olive residue gasification using silica sand is the risk of agglomeration, due to high content of alkali and alkaline-earth metals in the fuel. Lower melting point of these metal create melts with bed material, which results in defluidization. Water gasification, where steam is introduced as a part of gasifying media, dramatically increases CGE and GY.

For olivine, ER decrease also decreased GY, but had the opposite effect on CGE, where steam addition as the gasifying agent greatly improved both of these parameters. Temperature effect is also noticeable, where higher temperatures provide better quality and quantity of product gas. Another huge benefit of olivine as bed material as oppose to silica sand is that there were no signs of agglomeration as the tests were carried out even at higher temperatures, providing more stable conditions for gasification.

Product gas composition is also of great importance, as it directly affects the heating value of the syngas. Below you can find the tables of compositions of three main indicative components: H₂, CO, CO₂.

Table III: H₂ composition results

Conditions	H ₂ (%)				
	ER	0.35	0.317	0.283	0.25
Silica sand, T = 660 - 740°C	3.51	4.78	5.41	8.24	
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	-	-	10.49	
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	7.88	8.8	9.51	
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	13.6	
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	19.21	
Olivine, T = 750°C	-	7.65	10.21	14	
Olivine, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	19.59	
Olivine, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	24.6	
Olivine, T = 840°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	27.55	

H₂ (%) content increases as ER and Temperature increase. Steam addition also greatly increases H₂ content. Change of bed material also greatly improved H₂ content, allowing the production of higher heating value product gas.

Table IV: CO composition results

Conditions	CO (%)				
	ER	0.35	0.317	0.283	0.25
Silica sand, T = 660 - 740°C	9.32	8.34	7.58	8.79	
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	-	-	9.44	
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	10.07	10.17	10.07	
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	9.65	
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	9.44	
Olivine, T = 750°C	-	8.03	9.54	11.39	
Olivine, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	11.51	
Olivine, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	11.82	
Olivine, T = 840°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	15.91	

CO composition follow the same pattern as H₂, but steam introduction minorly decreases its content. CO₂ content behavior is exact opposite of CO, which makes sense, as gasification process always balances between complete and incomplete combustion.

Table V: CO₂ composition results

Conditions	CO ₂ (%)			
	ER	0.35	0.317	0.283
Silica sand, T = 660 - 740°C	17.62	17.16	16.34	14.7
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	-	-	13.19
Silica sand, T = 750°C	-	16.9	15.9	14.55
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	15.81
Silica sand, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	16.82
Olivine, T = 750°C	-	17.62	16.18	14.68
Olivine, T = 750°C, 14.71 wt% steam	-	-	-	15.76
Olivine, T = 750°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	16.33
Olivine, T = 840°C, 25.64 wt% steam	-	-	-	14.41

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study concerned the gasification of solid biomass from agricultural sector, represented by the olive oil mill residue. WOB lab-scale fluidized bed reactor at ECN, Netherlands was used for the purpose of the research. By changing gasification conditions such as ER, temperature, bed material and gasifying agent it was possible to observe their effect on the product gas composition, gas yield and cold gas efficiency. Those results, in fact, allowed to establish the gasification conditions, which are best suited for the chosen type fuel. As a result, ER = 0.25, temperature ranges 800-850, olivine as bed material and water gasification with 25.64wt% steam were defined as the appropriate conditions for olive residue gasification. With the above parameters, gasification process was providing the best quality syngas and dealt with agglomeration problem, which would otherwise arise when using feedstock with high alkali and alkaline-earth metals content.

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